

Optimized Monitoring of Underwater Marine Waste Using Knowledge Distillation

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Abstract—In this study, we present a method using knowledge distillation to create faster versions of deep architectures with fewer parameters for underwater marine waste classification. The proposed architectures, derived from VGG19, ResNet50, and DenseNet121, can independently classify images for remote monitoring with lower latency and improved performance. All deep models were trained on the JAMSTEC library of deep-sea images and compared with the original dense architectures that have higher parameter counts. The proposed models, with approximately 25% of the original deep architecture parameters, showed improved performance in terms of accuracy and inference time, achieving 70% accuracy through knowledge distillation.

Index Terms—Knowledge distillation, Edge computing, Convolution Neural Networks (CNN), latency, classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Monitoring marine pollution, particularly underwater marine waste, is crucial for maintaining healthy marine life. It is not only harmful for marine life, but sharp objects like glass and metal are hazardous for divers, can contaminate water, and damage boat propellers as well. However, monitoring of marine waste poses significant challenges due to the complex and dynamic nature of marine environments. Traditional methods often require manual inspection, which can be time-consuming, expensive and more human effort is required. During the last few years, Artificial Intelligence (AI) emerged as an alternative solution to perform less intensive monitoring of underwater marine waste. Recent advancements in the field of computer vision using AI based techniques have provided efficient solution in automating the detection and classification of underwater debris. Therefore, research focus has been directed towards the development of automated monitoring systems. More specifically, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) based deep architecture have shown promising results. Canals et al. conducted a comprehensive review of existing methods, highlighting key areas for the improvements and future challenges associated with seafloor litter monitoring systems [1]. Politikos et al. utilized a similar CNN-based approach for seafloor litter detection [2]. Marin et al. developed a model for autonomous marine debris identification and classification, further conducting a comparative analysis of various state-of-the-art deep convolutional architectures [3]. More recently, Walia and Pavithra provided a comprehensive survey of state-of-the-art architectures and existing datasets to establish a baseline for submerged waste

and trash detection [4]. Xue et al. presented the classification of deep-sea debris using deep convolutional neural networks and proposed Shuffle-Xception network model [5]. The model is trained on real deep-sea debris images and compared with previously proposed classification model. Similarly, Wei et al. proposed a modified U-Net-based architecture to perform end-to-end image semantic segmentation of underwater waste. Target-background imbalance problem was addressed through the data augmentation strategy and the focal loss function [6]. More recently, Chen et al. proposed a modified version of YOLOv5 network by replacing the structure with Shufflenetv2 network to detect marine waste from the surface of the water [7]. They mainly addressed the issue of slow computing speed and small storage space due to insufficient hardware resources of unmanned vehicles. Despite these significant advancements, achieving fully automated marine litter monitoring remains a challenge task. This is primarily attributed to the inherent diversity within marine litter categories and the considerable intra-class variations present. Additionally, these models are often complex and require significant computational resources, making them less suitable for real-world applications. Moreover, deploying these complex and large deep learning models on resource-constrained platforms is impractical due to their high computational requirements. To address these challenges, we explore the use of knowledge distillation to create lightweight deep learning models that can effectively classify marine pollution while maintaining high accuracy and efficiency. Through knowledge distillation, knowledge from a complex model termed as a *teacher*, can be transferred to a faster *student* model with fewer parameters. By transferring the knowledge from the teacher to the student, knowledge distillation allows models with fewer parameters to maintain high accuracy while requiring less computational resources. This makes them suitable for the deployment in resource-constrained environments, enabling real-time image classification for efficient marine pollution monitoring process.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: In Section II, we provide a detailed explanation of the dataset used for training and testing purposes. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and the architecture based on them are also discussed in this section. Section III discusses the results obtained from the network training and testing. We present a comparison of teacher and student networks with knowledge distillation. Section IV concludes the paper and suggests

Fig. 1. Images of each class sourced from JAMSTEC-library of Deep-Sea images.

Fig. 2. Knowledge distillation: illustration of loss function calculation for the teacher and student network, where q_T and q_S are noted as the likelihood distributions, when $t=1$. The $[/t]$ block indicates the division by t operation [14].

future extensions of the work.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Acquisition and Dataset

The dataset used in this work is sourced from the database of *The Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC)* [8], supplemented with Google images provided by the authors of [3]. The dataset comprises a total of 2,395 images belonging to six classes: *Glass*, *Metal*, *Plastic*, *Rubber*, *Other*, and *No trash*. To ensure a balanced distribution of classes between the training and test sets, the dataset for each class is divided accordingly. Therefore, 80% of the images within each class were used for training, while the remaining 20% within each class were allocated for evaluating the performance of each model. Fig.1 illustrates a sample of raw images from each class. All images were pre-processed using the corresponding *preprocess_input* function from the *tf.keras.applications* module before undergoing the training step on the respective deep architecture.

B. Knowledge Distillation

Knowledge distillation introduced by Hinton et al. [9] is a deep learning technique to transfer knowledge from a larger,

Fig. 3. The respective teacher and student network architectures are depicted. Dense and final *Softmax* classification layers for 6 classes are added to each teacher and student network.

more complex model termed as *teacher* to a smaller, efficient model termed as *student*. Thus, enables the student model to achieve performance levels close to those of the teacher model while utilizing fewer computational resources. For the

classification of images, let T and S be the teacher network and student network, respectively, for the same input \mathbf{x} . The pre-softmax logits z_T and z_S are tempered with the same temperature value t as [9]:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\mathbf{q}}_T &= \text{softmax}\left(\frac{\mathbf{z}_T}{t}\right), \\ \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_S &= \text{softmax}\left(\frac{\mathbf{z}_S}{t}\right),\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

where,

$$\text{softmax}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\exp(\mathbf{x}_j)}{\sum_i^{|\mathbf{x}|} \exp(\mathbf{x}_j)} \quad (2)$$

The student network is trained to match its tempered output $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}_S$ with the tempered softmax prediction $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}_T$ of the teacher network and match the q_S (denote $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}_S$ for $t=1$) with the ground truth \mathbf{p} for \mathbf{x}

$$\mathcal{L}_S = \mathcal{H}(\tilde{\mathbf{q}}_T, \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_S) + \alpha \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}_S), \quad (3)$$

where α is a trainable hyper-parameter to balance the two loss components, and \mathcal{H} denotes the cross-entropy loss function [10]. During the training process, the student network learns from both the true data labels and the *soft predictions* provided by the teacher network. These soft predictions are probabilistic outputs that offer additional information. During the training process, loss function combines the cross-entropy loss (between the predictions of student network and the true labels) with a distillation loss (between the prediction of student network with the soft prediction of teacher network) as illustrated in eq. 3. The graphical explanation of loss functions is given in Fig. 2. In the present study, we performed knowledge distillation from the pre-trained models to their smaller version when trained on the given underwater marine dataset.

C. Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for classification

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is among the most extensively studied deep learning based algorithm for image classification. CNNs process images given as an input by assigning weights to various objects within the image, thereby distinguishing them from one another with higher accuracy [11]. Gua *et al.* conducted an extensive survey of recent advancements in CNNs [11] for image classification. Each layer comprises of multiple convolution kernels that compute multiple feature maps. CNNs learn local features and generate maps containing extracted features by convolving the input image with a learned kernel, followed by element-wise nonlinear activation on the extracted features. The kernel is shared across all spatial locations of the input. Therefore, complete feature maps are obtained using several different kernels across different layers. Mathematically, the feature value at location (m, n) in the p -th feature map of the q -th layer, $v_{m,n,p}^q$, is calculated by:

$$v_{m,n,p}^q = (f_p^q)^T u_{m,n}^q + c_p^q$$

where f_p^q and c_p^q are the weight vector and bias term of the p -th filter of the q -th layer, respectively, and $u_{m,n}^q$ is the input patch centered at location (m, n) of the q -th layer. The activation value $h_{m,n,p}^q$ of the convolutional feature $v_{m,n,p}^q$ can be computed as:

$$h_{m,n,p}^q = g(v_{m,n,p}^q)$$

Pooling layers aggregate information within the feature map by replacing local pooling regions with the maximum element if max pooling is applied. The accurate performance of deep learning based algorithms depends on the availability of training data. Acquiring large datasets for underwater marine waste detection is challenging due to the dynamic environmental conditions. Not only that acquiring data under the sea/ocean is expensive and challenging task due to the diversity of marine habitats, ranging from shallow coastal waters to deep-sea environments. Consequently, transfer learning based approaches are extensively deployed for the classification task along with data augmentation techniques. The CNN module for each teacher network utilizes three deep learning architectures: VGG19, DenseNet121, and ResNet50, chosen for their effectiveness in distilling knowledge for underwater marine waste classification. In the following subsections, we provide concise overviews of these architectures. The illustration of these teacher and their respective student networks is shown in Fig. 3.

1) *VGG19*: VGGNet, proposed by Karen Simonyan and Andrew Zisserman in 2014, is a standard deep CNN architecture with multiple layers [12]. VGGNet improves upon previous models by replacing larger filters with the sequences of smaller 3x3 filters and added more deeper networks with additional non-linearities. For instance, a stack of three 3x3 convolution layers (stride 1) has the same effective receptive field as a single 7x7 convolution layer. The use of multiple smaller layers allows for more non-linear activation layers alongside the convolution layers and enable the network to converge faster. VGG19 comprises 19 trainable layers in a feed-forward manner, including 16 convolution layers, 3 fully connected layers, 5 max-pooling layers, and a final softmax layer. While VGGNets have improved the performance of CNN-based models with high generalization ability, but large number of trainable parameters leads to exploding gradients issue.

Metric	Formula
Accuracy	$\frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$
Precision	$\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$
Recall	$\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$
F1-score	$2 * \frac{P * R}{P + R}$

TABLE I
EVALUATION METRICS FOR IMAGE CLASSIFICATION.

2) *ResNet50*: ResNet50, a CNN architecture introduced by He *et al.* in 2015 [13], incorporated skip connections to address vanishing gradients problem. These connections allow

data to bypass intermediate layers and flow directly through or around them. ResNet50 introduces the residual blocks where the activation of a layer are connected to subsequent layers via skip connections and addresses the degradation in training accuracy caused by vanishing gradients. ResNet50 is structured with 48 convolutional layers, along with one MaxPool layer and one average pool layer. It employs a bottleneck design for its building blocks, utilizing 1×1 convolutions to reduce the number of parameters and thereby accelerate the training process.

3) *DenseNet121*: DenseNets, short for Densely Connected Convolutional Networks, were introduced by Huang et al. in 2017 [14] as a notable advancement in deep convolutional networks. They effectively address the challenge of vanishing gradients in deep networks by implementing a dense connectivity pattern. In a DenseNet, each layer within a dense block connects directly to subsequent layers. This dense interconnection ensures that every layer receives input from all preceding layers, promoting robust feature reuse and enhancing gradient flow throughout the network. Transition layers are incorporated after dense blocks to reduce the depth and spatial size of the input volume. All these architectures are considered as a *Teacher* network and the student networks are shallow versions of their respective teacher networks, with the use of less number of convolution filters as illustrated in Fig. 3. Each student network is composed of a fully connected layers, followed by a standard softmax layer integrated for knowledge distillation training. This reduction in parameters makes the student networks significantly lighter (fewer parameters as given in Table III) compared to their teacher counterparts, rendering them suitable for efficient execution on edge devices.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the implementation purposes, we used Python 3.9.16 and the TensorFlow 2.6.0 machine learning framework, leveraging the TensorFlow.Keras API. All models were trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of $lr = 10^{-4}$, $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$, and $\epsilon = 10^{-7}$. To accommodate the larger models within the available resources, we maintained a batch size of 16. On top of the fixed layers used for feature extraction, a new classifier based on a new neural network is added to learn underlying patterns from extracted features of litter images and discriminate data according to them. All models were evaluated on the testing set using standard performance metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, and

F1-score. The mathematical formulation of these metrics is given in Table I. where TP is true positive, TN corresponds to true negative, FP indicates false positive, and FN represents false negative. Additionally, P represents precision and R corresponds to recall.

Table II summarizes the performance metrics of VGG19, DenseNet121, and ResNet50 models both with and without ImageNet pre-training weights. Pre-trained with ImageNet weights consistently performed better than the same architectures without pre-training across all evaluated metrics. DenseNet121 exhibits the highest overall performance, achieving the highest validation accuracy of 84.28% and F1-score of 84.21% when pre-trained with ImageNet weights. VGG19, achieved the accuracy of 78.62%, with lower precision, recall, and F1-score compared to DenseNet121 and ResNet50. The obtained results highlighted the effectiveness of transfer learning using ImageNet weights in enhancing model performance for the classification of under water marine waste. Therefore, we selected these pre-trained models as a teacher network to distill knowledge.

Fig. 4. Performance in terms of accuracy of models in different scenarios: teacher network, student network, distillation with varying temperature values (T=4 and T=6)

Fig. 4 presents accuracy results for DenseNet121, VGG19, and ResNet50 models in different scenarios. The pre-trained teacher models, DenseNet121 and ResNet50, achieve the highest accuracies of 84.28% and 83.23%, respectively, representing the robust performance of these models. In contrast, the student models, simpler versions of their teacher architectures, exhibited relatively lower performance. DenseNet121 at 63.31% and ResNet50 at 58.49%. However, these student

Model	Weights	Val-Acc	Precision	Recall	F1-score
VGG19		64.78	65.8	64.78	64.84
DenseNet121	without ImageNet weights	63.31	63.9	63.31	63.25
ResNet50		58.49	61.11	58.49	57.89
VGG19		78.62	75.69	75.47	75.23
DenseNet121	ImageNet weights	84.28	84.68	85.01	84.21
ResNet50		83.23	83.26	83.23	83.22

TABLE II

THE COMPARISON OF PERFORMANCE IN TERMS OF EVALUATION METRICS BETWEEN PRE-TRAINED TEACHER NETWORKS AND NETWORKS TRAINED WITHOUT IMAGENET WEIGHTS.

network performed better than their teacher network with out pre-trained ImageNet weights given in Table II. Through distillation, where knowledge from the pre-trained teacher models is transferred to the students, hence improved the performance of student networks. We performed distillation at varying temperature and observed that distillation at T=6 consistently yields higher accuracies compared to T=4 across three networks, demonstrating that softer probability distributions during training enable more effective knowledge transfer. For instance, the distilled models with T=6 achieve accuracies of 69.39% for DenseNet121, 68.9% for VGG19, and 65.72% for ResNet50, indicating significant performance enhancements over the student models. The obtained results indicate the effectiveness of knowledge distillation in enhancing the performance of lighter models.

Model	Parameters	Accuracy (%)	Time (ms)
DenseNet121	7.04M	69.39	249
DenseNet121- Light	943K	63.31	54
VGG19	20M	59.33	633
VGG19 - Light	6M	67.08	166
ResNet50	23.5M	59.33	271
ResNet50 - Light	7.3M	63.31	110

TABLE III

COMPARISON OF STUDENT NETWORKS WITH THEIR LIGHTER VERSIONS IN TERMS OF EVALUATION METRICS, INFERENCE TIME AND PARAMETERS. FOR EACH MODEL, THE CORRESPONDING PRE-TRAINED NETWORK, USING IMAGENET DATASET WEIGHTS, PERFORMED AS THE TEACHER NETWORK. INFERENCE TIME OF EACH MODEL IS COMPUTED ON NVIDIA TESLA T4 (TU104) PROCESSOR.

Table III compares the networks with their lighter versions on multiple benchmarks *e.g.*, parameter count, accuracy, and inference time. DenseNet121 has 7.04M parameters, achieves 69.39% accuracy, and takes 249 ms for inference. Its lighter variant, DenseNet121-Light, with 943K parameters, achieves 63.31% accuracy in 54 ms. VGG19 (20M parameters) achieves 59.33% accuracy in 633 ms, while VGG19-Light (6M parameters) achieves 67.08% accuracy in 166 ms. ResNet50 (23.5M parameters) achieves 59.33% accuracy in 271 ms, whereas ResNet50-Light (7.3M parameters) maintains 63.31% accuracy but reduces inference time to 110 ms. To summarize, table indicates that *Light* versions of the networks provide a reasonable balance between accuracy and inference speed. While they are slightly less accurate than their original networks but their reduced complexity allows them to reduce the inference time. This makes them suitable for applications where the issues related to the latency is of extreme importance and also in resource constrained environment.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we explored the feasibility of applying knowledge distillation to train lighter versions of CNNs based deep architectures for the classification of underwater images. To augment the dataset, we employed various augmentation techniques, including random rotations, shearing, brightness, and horizontal flipping during the training process. Three teacher networks and their respective student networks were

trained using a real underwater image dataset containing waste items. We conducted distillation at varying temperatures and observed that a temperature of T=6 consistently yields higher accuracies compared to T=4 across all three networks. This demonstrates that softer probability distributions during training enable more effective knowledge transfer. The student architectures, based on VGG19, ResNet50, and DenseNet121, demonstrated comparable performance compared to their teacher network. fewer parameters and faster inference times. The reduction in complexity not only decreases the computational resources required but also significantly improves the inference time, making the distilled networks suitable for the deployment on resource-constrained edge devices and for real-time applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This study has been funded by the project CLEVER (Project ID 101097560), that is supported by the Key Digital Technologies Joint Undertaking and its members (including top-up funding by Italian Ministry of University and Research — MUR).

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